

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of the performance and quality of nursing services on the satisfaction of patients in the inpatient room at Mokoyurli Hospital Buol, Indonesia

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Abstract

The study aims to analyze the effect of performance and quality of nursing service on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of Mokoyurli Hospital, Buol. This research is using a quantitative analytic survey design with a cross-sectional approach. The subject was determined using the Slovin formula and obtained a number of 80 people. Data were collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analysis. The statistical tests used were chi-square and simple regression tests. The results showed that performance and quality of nursing services influence patient satisfaction with a p-value of 0.000. Multivariate analysis showed the dominant factor influencing the satisfaction of patients is the quality of services with an OR value of 33.269. Therefore, it is recommended that the Mokoyurli Hospital conduct training or workshops for health workers to improve the quality of service that must be improved, especially tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, to address patient complaints in the inpatient unit of Mokoyurli Hospital, Buol.

Keywords: Patient Satisfaction; Employee Performance; Service Quality; Inpatient room

1. Introduction

Hospitals are an integral part of the health care system that is regulated through health development plans and cannot be separated from national health development policies. According to Rikomah (2017), hospitals have duties and functions based on Law No. 44 of 2009 concerning Hospitals. The task of the hospital is to carry out health services efforts efficiently and effectively, by prioritizing healing and recovery which is carried out in a harmonious and integrated manner, with improvement and prevention, as well as the implementation of referral efforts. Hospitals also have the task of providing comprehensive individual health services.

A nurse is one of the professions that plays an important role in efforts to maintain the quality of health services in hospitals. In the standard of evaluation and quality control, it is explained that nursing services ensure the existence of high-quality nursing care and continuously involve themselves in control programs in hospitals (Nugraha, et al., 2015). The performance of nurses is measured by the services provided to patients to provide satisfaction to patients. Nurse performance is the level of success of nurses in providing nursing care following their duties and responsibilities (Kurniadi, 2013). Good nurse performance is a guarantee of the quality of health services provided to patients. Through the performance of nurses, they are expected to demonstrate their professional contribution to improving the quality of nursing services, which will have an impact on health services and the quality of life and welfare of the community (Luan, et al., 2018).

The most important aspect of patient satisfaction is nursing care because nurses interact with patients more often than other health workers. About 85% of health service problems are in the implementation of services, which, the problem

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is the quality of nursing services. The level of public satisfaction with health services is obtained from the results of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM). The results of the IKM survey conducted in 2019 showed that the level of patient satisfaction with services in the inpatient room was 79.22% in the good category but had not yet reached the Minimum Service Standards (SPM) for hospitalization, which was > 90%. Meanwhile, currently, the responsiveness index is in the value range of 6.8 and the target in 2019 is 8. Responsiveness is a service carried out by a nursing service officer with a quick response to meet patient needs related to improving individual or group welfare through nursing actions (Apriyani & Sureskiarti, 2021).

The results of a preliminary survey conducted by researchers in September 2022 by conducting brief interviews with patients who were hospitalized at RSUD Mokoyurli Buol, they complained about services that were considered slow, the response of less friendly health workers, and an uncomfortable environment. In addition, there were also reports of other health workers who complained in the nursing field with a description of the performance of several colleagues who were less compliant with the schedule and shift of service, and there were also nurses who were busy with their cellphones at the nurse station.

Based on this explanation, the researcher is interested in conducting a study with the title "The Effect of Performance and Quality of Nursing Services on Patient Satisfaction in the Inpatient Room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol." The purpose of this study was to analyze the performance and quality of nurse services on patient satisfaction, especially patients in the inpatient room.

2. Methods

This study uses quantitative analytical research methods with a cross-sectional approach. This study involves independent variables in the form of nurse performance (X_1) and service quality (X_2) as independent variables, and patient satisfaction (Y) as the dependent variable. The research sample was a total of 80 patients in inpatient services at RSUD Mokoyurli Buol, the number of patients was determined based on the Slovin formula. The research data were collected through interviews, documentation, distribution of questionnaires, and measurements. The data were then analyzed using the chi-square test method.

3. Results

3.1. Univariate Analysis

3.1.1. Nurse performance distribution

The variable of nurse performance was assessed based on 4 indicators, namely discipline, integrity, service orientation, and cooperation. The distribution of nurses' performance based on each indicator can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1 Frequency Distribution of Performance Based on Each Indicator

Indicator	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Performance Based on Discipline		
Discipline	57	71.3
Lack of Discipline	23	28.8
Total	80	100
Performance Based on Integrity		
With Integrity	48	60.0
Lack of Integrity	32	40.0
Total	80	100
Performance Based on Services Orientation		
Good	43	53.8
Poor	37	46.3

Total	80	100
Performance Based on Cooperation		
Good	47	58.8
Poor	33	41.3
Total	80	100

Source: Primary data, 2023

3.2. Distribution of quality of service

Service quality variables are assessed based on 5 indicators, namely tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The distribution of service quality based on each indicator can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 Frequency Distribution of Service Quality Based on Each Indicator

Indicator	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Quality of Service Based on Tangible		
Good	45	56.3
Poor	35	43.8
Total	80	100
Quality of Service Based on Reliability		
Good	43	53.8
Poor	37	46.3
Total	80	100
Quality of Service Based on Responsiveness		
Good	53	66.3
Poor	27	33.8
Total	80	100
Quality of Service Based on Assurance		
Good	43	53.8
Poor	37	46.3
Total	80	100
Quality of Service Based on Empathy		
Good	48	60.0
Poor	32	40.0
Total	80	100

Source: Primary data, 2023

3.3. Bivariate Analysis

This analysis was carried out to test the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable using the chi-square test. The chi-square test is a test that compares the frequency that occurs (observation) with the expected frequency (expectation). If the observation frequency value and the expected frequency value are the same, it is said that there is no significant difference (significant). Vice versa, if the observation frequency value and the expected frequency value are different, then it is said that there is a significant difference.

3.3.1. The effect of nurse performance on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol

The effect of nurse performance on patient satisfaction is assessed based on 4 indicators, namely discipline, integrity, service orientation, and cooperation. The results of the analysis of the effect of nurse performance on patient satisfaction are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Analysis of the Effect of Nurse Performance on Patient Satisfaction in the Inpatient Room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol

Indicator	Patient Satisfaction				Total		p-value
	Satisfied	%	Less Satisfied	%	N	%	
Nurse Performance							
Good	37	46.3	9	11.3	46	47.5	0.000
Poor	5	6.3	29	36.3	34	42.5	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Discipline							
Discipline	40	50.0	17	21.3	57	71.3	0.000
Lack of Discipline	2	2.5	21	26.3	23	28.8	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Integrity							
With Integrity	36	45.0	12	15.0	48	60.0	0.000
Lack of Integrity	6	7.5	26	32.5	32	40.0	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Services Orientation							
Good	34	42.5	9	11.3	43	53.8	0.000
Poor	8	10.0	29	36.3	37	46.3	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Cooperation							
Good	35	43.8	12	15.0	47	58.8	0.000
Poor	7	8.8	26	32.5	33	41.3	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2023

Based on the results in Table 3, of the four indicators of assessing the effect of nurse performance on patient satisfaction, the better each indicator, the higher the patient satisfaction. From the statistical test results, a p-value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. Thus, it can be said that there is an effect of nurse performance on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol.

3.4. Effect of service quality on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol

The effect of service quality on patient satisfaction is assessed based on 5 indicators, namely tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The results of the analysis of the effect of service quality on patient satisfaction are presented in Table 4.

Based on the results in Table 4, of the five indicators assessing the effect of service quality on patient satisfaction, the better each indicator, the higher the patient satisfaction. From the statistical test results, the p-value = 0.000 is obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. Thus, it can be said that there is an effect of service quality on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol.

Table 4 Analysis of the Effect of Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction in the Inpatient Room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol

Indicator	Patient Satisfaction				Total		p-value
	Satisfied	%	Less Satisfied	%	N	%	
Service Quality							
Good	35	43.8	5	6.3	40	50	0.000
Poor	7	8.8	33	41.3	40	50	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Tangible							
Good	29	36.3	16	20.0	45	56.3	0.015
Poor	13	16.3	22	27.5	35	43.8	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Reliability							
Good	32	40.0	11	13.8	43	53.8	0.000
Poor	10	12.5	27	33.8	37	46.3	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Responsiveness							
Good	37	46.3	16	20.0	53	66.3	0.000
Poor	5	6.3	22	27.5	27	33.8	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Assurance							
Good	33	41.3	10	12.5	43	53.8	0.000
Poor	9	11.3	28	35.0	37	46.3	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	
Empathy							
Good	36	45.0	12	15.0	48	60.0	0.000
Poor	6	7.5	26	32.5	32	40.0	
Total	42	52.5	38	47.5	80	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2023

3.5. Multivariate Analysis

Table 5 Analysis of the Effect of Nurse Performance and Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction

No.	Research Variables	p-value	Odds Ratio	95% C.I for EXP (B)	
				Lower	Upper
1	Nurse Performance	0.000	24.056	4.511	128.280
2	Services Quality	0.000	33.269	6.433	172.048

Source: Primary data, 2023

This analysis aims to determine the independent variable that dominantly affects the dependent variable. The analysis was conducted using a simple regression test. The results of multivariate analysis are presented in Table 5. The results

in Table 5 show that the most dominant variable affecting patient satisfaction is service quality with an odds ratio of 33.269.

4. Discussion

4.1. Analysis of the Effect of Performance on Patient Satisfaction in the Inpatient Room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol

Nursing performance is the result of nursing services that determine the quality of health services and determine the image of health service institutions in the eyes of the community. The results of research conducted at RSUD Mokoyurli Buol showed that out of 80 respondents, 46 of them had good performance, while 34 other respondents had poor performance. The statistical test results provide a p-value = 0.000, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of nurse performance on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol.

The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Fardhoni et al. (2021). The results of his research indicate that nursing services and nurse performance have a positive and significant influence on patient satisfaction at Sumber Kasih Cirebon Hospital. This can be seen from the t_{count} value of the two variables which is greater than the t_{table} and the F_{count} value which is greater than the F_{table} at the $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level. In addition, the results showed that nursing service variables and nurse performance simultaneously influenced patient satisfaction by 92.9%, while the other 7.1% was influenced by other factors.

Based on observations, it was found that some nurses had poor performance. The system of providing rewards and punishments for nurse performance has not been carried out optimally, so this affects nurse performance. The hospital management supervision and evaluation system implemented also did not follow the standard procedures issued by the Regional Personnel Agency of Buol Regency. According to researchers, there is a need for assertiveness and supervision from hospital management to apply the rules that have been set to be obeyed together.

4.1.1. Nursing performance in terms of discipline

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 57 respondents were categorized as disciplined, while 23 respondents were less disciplined. The patient satisfaction assessment showed that of the respondents who fell into the disciplined category, 40 of them were satisfied, while 17 others gave an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fall into the less disciplined category shows that as many as 2 respondents are satisfied, while 21 others give an unsatisfied assessment. From the statistical test results, a p-value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an influence of nurse discipline on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with Safrina's research (2017) whose results show that there is a significant influence of work discipline on employee performance.

Based on observations, researchers found that there were nurses who were not disciplined in providing services. Forms of indiscipline that are carried out include not attending morning roll calls, often being late for work, and not following official shifts for various reasons. Work discipline greatly affects the performance of nurses because discipline is a form of training for nurses in implementing the rules in the hospital. Work discipline is an operative function of management in organizing and controlling human resources. The better the work discipline, the higher the work performance.

4.1.2. Nursing performance in terms of integrity

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 48 respondents were categorized as having integrity, while 32 respondents lacked integrity. The assessment of patient satisfaction shows that of the respondents who fall into the category of integrity, 36 of them are satisfied, while 12 others give a less satisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fall into the category of lack of integrity shows that as many as 6 respondents are satisfied, while 26 others give a less satisfied assessment. From the statistical test results, a p-value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of nurse integrity on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with the research of Banunaek, et al. (2021) whose results show that nurse professionalism has a positive effect on service quality, while ethical dilemmas change the effect of nurse professionalism and reduce the quality of nursing services.

According to the researchers, integrity needs to be present in a nurse in building partnerships, trust, and commitment between patients and health workers in providing professional nursing services. Some nurses have poor integrity due

to work pressure, economic life, family problems, and so on that affect their integrity at work so that the trust of colleagues and patients in them is reduced. Integrity is a picture of self in work, abilities, behavior, and daily actions.

4.1.3. Nursing performance in terms of services orientation

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 43 respondents were categorized as having good service orientation, while the other 37 respondents had poor service orientation. The patient satisfaction assessment showed that of the respondents who fell into the good service-oriented category, 34 of them were satisfied, while the other 9 gave an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fell into the category of poor service orientation showed that as many as 8 respondents were satisfied, while 29 others gave an unsatisfied assessment. The statistical test result gives a p-value = 0.000, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of nurse service orientation on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with the research of Akmal, et al. (2022) whose results show that there is a positive influence of service orientation at work on patient satisfaction.

Service orientation is the attitude and work behavior of nurses in providing the best service to those served, including patients (community), colleagues, and related work units. The work culture of the treatment room, which involves multidisciplinary science and professions, requires health workers to work respectfully and communicatively according to their respective expertise and competence.

4.1.4. Nursing performance in terms of cooperation

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 47 respondents were categorized as having good cooperation, while 33 respondents had poor cooperation. The assessment of patient satisfaction showed that of the respondents who fell into the category of good cooperation, 35 of them were satisfied, while 12 others gave an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fell into the category of poor cooperation showed that 7 respondents were satisfied, while 26 others gave an unsatisfactory assessment. From the statistical test results, a p-value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of nurse cooperation on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with the research of Siregar, et al. (2020) whose results show that the work team and competence partially and simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on nurse performance.

Cooperation is necessary in building a solid team, building togetherness, and work commitment to achieve goals as expected. Without good cooperation between colleagues and other health workers, it will cause a decrease in patient satisfaction due to the adverse effects of lack of cooperation which causes customer (patient) complaints. Cooperation in the performance of nurses in the inpatient room includes official shift passes, delegation of actions, education, patient transfers, recording in medical records, and so on.

4.2. Analysis of the Effect of Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction in the Inpatient Room of Mokoyurli Buol Hospital

Nursing service quality is a process of activities carried out by the nursing profession to meet the needs of patients in maintaining the state of the patient's biological, psychological, and spiritual aspects (Suarli & Bahtiar, 2012). Indicators of nursing service quality include patient safety, self-care, patient satisfaction, anxiety, comfort, and knowledge. The results of research conducted at RSUD Mokoyurli Buol showed that out of 80 respondents, 40 of them had good service quality, while the other 40 respondents had poor performance. The statistical test results provide a p-value = 0.000, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of nursing service quality on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Fadila & Sulastri (2023). The results of his research show a p-value = 0.002, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. So, it is concluded that there is a close relationship between service quality and elderly patient satisfaction at the internal medicine clinic of Siti Fatimah Hospital.

Service quality is assessed based on 5 indicators, namely tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Based on observations made by researchers, in terms of appearance, some officers still look untidy. In terms of reliability, the reliability of officers is uneven according to their competence. In terms of responsiveness, officers are considered slow in serving complaints or complaints from patients. In terms of assurance, it is also considered to be lacking because the privacy of patients in the ward treatment room is not maintained due to the slightly open condition of the ward. In terms of empathy, officers are considered still lacking because there are still officers who like to play online gaming while on duty, so attention and concern for patients are slightly reduced.

4.2.1. *Quality of service in terms of tangible*

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 45 respondents were categorized as good tangibles, while 35 other respondents had poor tangibles. The patient satisfaction assessment showed that of the respondents who fell into the good tangible category, 29 of them were satisfied, while 16 others gave an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents in the poor tangible category showed that 13 of them were satisfied, while 22 others gave an unsatisfied assessment. From the statistical test results, a p-value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an influence of tangible on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with Kamil's research (2011) whose results show a relationship between patient satisfaction and the appearance of nurses at Banda Aceh Hospital. The appearance of a cleaner and tidier nurse will cause patients to feel comfortable and interested in communicating well.

Researchers argue that the physical form of nursing services is an important thing in determining the satisfaction of patients who receive nursing services. The quality of service from the tangible dimension greatly affects the visual or visible. This is evidenced by the results of interviews with several patients in the treatment room who said that seeing officers who are neat, clean, beautiful, and fragrant encourages those who lie weak in the hospital, especially if accompanied by a friendly, polite, communicative attitude in greeting, and interacting with patients.

4.2.2. *Quality of service in terms of reliability*

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 43 respondents were categorized as having good reliability, while 37 other respondents had poor reliability. The patient satisfaction assessment shows that of the respondents who fall into the good reliability category, 32 of them are satisfied, while 11 others give an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fall into the category of poor reliability shows that as many as 10 respondents are satisfied, while 27 others give a less satisfied assessment. From the statistical test results, a p-value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of reliability on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with the research of Rahayu, et al. (2023) whose results show that partially and simultaneously the dimensions of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy have a significant positive effect on patient satisfaction of outpatient registration at Nur Hidayah Hospital.

The quality of service in the reliability dimension is the ability to provide reliable and accurate services. Workers are said to have high reliability if the performance provided by workers, in this case nurses, is following patient expectations. The performance expected by patients includes fast and precise patient acceptance, fast and precise examination services, correct and appropriate treatment, fast and precise care services, properly executed hospital service schedules, such as doctor visits, hospital service schedules are carried out quickly, service procedures are straightforward, and nurses are always ready to provide services according to procedures when needed by patients.

4.2.3. *Quality of service in terms of responsiveness*

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 53 respondents were categorized with good responsiveness, while 27 other respondents had poor responsiveness. The patient satisfaction assessment shows that of the respondents who fall into the good responsiveness category, 37 of them are satisfied, while 16 others give an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fall into the category of poor responsiveness shows that as many as 5 respondents are satisfied, while 22 others give a less satisfied assessment. From the statistical test results, a p-value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of responsiveness on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with Agustina's research (2023) whose results show that responsiveness has a partial and simultaneous effect on patient satisfaction.

Responsiveness in inpatient services greatly affects quality improvement and patient safety in hospitals. The quality of service in terms of responsiveness is the ability of officers to provide responsive services. This dimension emphasizes the attention and speed of the officers involved in responding to patient requests, questions, and complaints. Other forms of responsiveness are intravenous administration, emergency drug administration, wound care, shock management, transfusion administration, and other actions that require fast movement in accordance with response time in nursing services.

4.2.4. *Quality of service in terms of assurance*

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 43 respondents were categorized as good assurance, while 37 other respondents had poor assurance. The assessment of patient satisfaction shows that of the respondents who fall into the

good assurance category, 33 of them are satisfied, while 10 others give an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fall into the category of poor assurance shows that as many as 9 respondents are satisfied, while 28 others give a less satisfied assessment. From the statistical test results, the p -value = 0.000 is obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of assurance on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is in line with the research of Darado, et al. (2023) whose results show that the quality of nurse service is quite good, so it is necessary to strive to improve the quality of nurse service through maximum supervision and evaluation.

Ensuring the confidentiality of medical records, insurance coverage, and sensitive matters when performing nursing actions greatly affects the quality of service and privacy of a patient. This is regulated in the regulation of patient rights and obligations and is well explained when the patient is admitted to the hospital. Assurance has a positive relationship with patient satisfaction. The better the consumer's perception of the guarantee provided, the higher the patient's satisfaction. If the guarantee of the quality of service received or felt is lower than expected, then the quality of health services will be perceived as poor or unsatisfactory. Therefore, whether the quality of service is good or not depends on the service provider's ability to consistently meet patient expectations.

4.2.5. Quality of service in terms of empathy

The results showed that out of 80 respondents, 48 respondents were categorized as having good empathy, while 32 other respondents had poor empathy. The patient satisfaction assessment showed that of the respondents who fell into the good empathy category, 36 of them were satisfied, while 12 others gave an unsatisfied assessment. The assessment for respondents who fell into the category of poor empathy showed that as many as 6 respondents were satisfied, while 26 others gave an unsatisfied assessment. From the statistical test results, a p -value = 0.000 was obtained, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. It can be said that there is an effect of empathy on patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of the Mokoyurli Buol Hospital. This is in line with Dewi's research (2023), the results of which show that there is a relationship between the perceived quality of the empathy aspect and patient satisfaction.

Measuring the quality of service in the caring dimension can be seen from the ease of communication, the ease of interacting with health workers, and the ease of obtaining information, so that patients feel safe, comfortable, and calm in hospital care. The caring side of the officer will be manifested in a patient attitude in handling patients, always providing motivation and encouragement to patients so that patients are strong and eager to recover, friendly and friendly, and act soothingly.

4.3. Analysis of the Most Dominant Risk Factors on Patient Satisfaction

The results of multivariate analysis show that the most dominant variable affecting patient satisfaction is service quality with an odds ratio of 33.269. This is in line with research conducted by Afriani, et al. (2023) which states that there is an influence of reliability, responsiveness, direct evidence, empathy, and assurance variables on health service satisfaction.

Health services are efforts made individually or together in an organization to maintain and improve health, prevent and treat disease, and restore health, aimed at individuals, groups, and communities. Nursing services are the main services of hospital services. This is because nursing services are provided for 24 hours to patients in need, in contrast to medical services and other health services that only require a relatively short time to provide health services to clients. Thus, nursing services need to be improved continuously and continuously so that hospital services will improve along with the increasing quality of nursing services.

The quality of hospital nursing services can be influenced by the assessment of patients as hospital customers. Assessment is a systematic way of experience to improve achievement, implementation, and planning. Service is said to be good if it is in accordance with what is expected and needed by customers.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the performance of nurses and the quality of nursing services affect patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol. This is evidenced by the results of statistical analysis which gives a p -value = 0.000, which, this value is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. The multivariate analysis results show that the most dominant variable affecting patient satisfaction in the inpatient room of RSUD Mokoyurli Buol is the service quality variable with an odds ratio of 33.269.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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